

EXPLORING THE UTILIZATION OF PERFORMANCE TASK ACTIVITY: ITS IMPLEMENTATION AND USEFULNESS IN TEACHING COLLEGE STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITY OF LA SALETTE, INC.

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the utilization of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) in terms of its implementation, usefulness, and challenges in teaching college students at University of La Salette, Inc. A descriptive-normative research design was employed with 20 instructors selected through random sampling who met the study criteria. A structured questionnaire was utilized to collect data on teacher's personal profile and rating of the qualities of effective teaching, level of perceived usefulness of PTE, the level of implementation, and also the challenges faced in the implementation. Descriptive and inferential statistics including weighted mean, t-test, and Pearson's r were used for data analysis. The instrument demonstrated good reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.86. The findings revealed that instructors fully implemented key effective teaching qualities, particularly preparation, organization, and mastery of subject matter. In terms of utility, PTE was rated as useful to very useful across academic, instructional, and attitudinal domains. It was found to enhance students' skills, responsibility for learning, and motivation, while also facilitating teachers' instructional practices. Although instructors experienced moderate challenges related to supervision, technical support, and increased workload, these did not hinder PTE implementation. Significant differences in perceived challenges were observed based on sex and civil status. Moreover, a significant positive relationship was found between the extent of PTE implementation and

its perceived usefulness. The study concludes that PTE is a feasible, beneficial, and sustainable assessment approach that supports learner-centered and outcomes-based practices in Philippine higher education institutions.

Keywords: *Performance Task Activity, Usefulness, Utilization, Teaching, College Students*

INTRODUCTION

Very recently, there have been changes in assessment practices with an increase in learner-centered and authentic assessments that focus on knowledge application in real-life situations. Within the shift in assessment practices, there have been activities involving performance tasks. This is especially true since assessments have been criticized for their inability to assess various components of learning that include higher-order thinking, critical thinking, and the ability to transfer and solve problems (Petalla & Doromal, 2021). Performance tasks require students to design and build responses, products, or activities that show and perform deep understanding and practical skills.

The educational impact of correctly applied performance task activities has been widely documented since 2021. In the Philippine context, according to Petalla and Doromal (2021) they have identified the introduction of performance task assessment as a component of educational reform to foster real world competence and 21st century skills. In his/her/their qualitative inquiry, the author states performance tasks assess the ability of students to apply and transfer learning. However, students experienced challenges related to task planning, execution and evaluation. These findings show that even though performance tasks have great instructional potential, the overall effectiveness of a performance task is determined by the way in which it is designed, implemented and sustained in the classroom.

Research has also shown that at the instructional level, genuine performance tasks have a positive impact on students' learning and the development of their overall professional competencies. According to the study of Uluçınar and Dinç (2021) noted that genuine performance tasks in undergraduate courses enhanced students' self-efficacy, teamwork, and communication, and motivation, as well as their ability to integrate theory and practice. Students reported that these tasks were enjoyable, original, and constructive, especially when the tasks were designed to simulate real life situations. This study demonstrates that performance tasks serve many purposes, and in addition to being assessment tools, they are essential instructional components that improve the quality of learning in post-secondary education.

Further evidence can be seen in the research on integrative and task-based assessments. Supported by the study of Rafael and Tabernilla (2023) on the integrative performance task assessment and noted that such tasks promote higher-order thinking since learners have to integrate knowledge from different content areas and use the same in a real-life situation. Based on the study, teachers benefitted from the use of performance tasks in boosting learning outcomes among students. However, there were

issues of workload, planning, and variations in implementation. Based on the findings, performance task activities are used due to proper planning as well as preparation of teachers. Research published in the same time frame has shown similar findings. A systematic review conducted by Xie and Lan (2025), of task-based teaching approaches, concluded that such methods, centered on the learner, and contextualized, improve engagement, self-confidence, and constructive practical skills. The review, however, concluded that the effectiveness of tasks depends on the type of instructional design, the institutional support, and the training that the teacher has received, and therefore, contextualized implementation strategies are needed in higher education. There is a considerable amount of literature that is still recent and supports the existence of performance task activities, however, in addition to this, it almost seems that there is a contradiction in the implementation of the performance task activities, and the outcomes that they yield. Hidalgo et al. (2025), describe the most hands-on and performance-based strategies as effective, provided there are defined instructional goals, and assessment criteria. The study also stated that it is the quality of the implementation that will determine the effectiveness of the performance tasks in enhancing, of which there should be many, student competencies. This further supports the idea that the performance tasks should be studied as to how they are executed and how the learners perceive them.

Thus, a need to examine the use of performance task activities in specific contexts of higher education institution. The University of La Sallette use of performance tasks is being integrated more and more into teaching at the college level. However, there is little empirical evidence of the implementation and or usefulness of performance tasks from a teaching and learning perspective. Therefore, it is crucial to examine the level of use of performance task activities and the degree to which they impact the students' learning experience to support the enhancement of teaching strategies, the alignment of assessments with intended learning outcomes, and the improvement of the overall teaching and learning activities in higher education. This study attempts to investigate the use of performance task activities, focusing on their implementation and usefulness in teaching college students at University of La Salette. By initiating the study from this perspective, the intention is to provide evidence- based support for the improvement of teaching, assessment, and policy in the practice of higher education.

Literature Review

Implementation of Performance Task Activities in Teaching and Learning

According to the latest studies, the majority of learner-centric and outcome-based educational frameworks place a strong emphasis on performance tasks. This is due to the fact that performance tasks enable students to articulate their learning in 'real' and relevant contexts, which are also meaningful. Within the Philippine context, study shows that most of the performance-based tasks as part of the curriculum reform efforts that aimed at measuring the competencies of the students and especially the higher order thinking skills, the 21st century skills. Petalla and Doromal (2021) claimed that implementation of performance-based assessment was meant to effect the shift of assessment practices from the traditional testing to the more authentic modes of assessing learning. Though the authors showed that with unclear instructions and limited

teacher guidance, the students faced challenges in planning, completing and assessing these tasks

Masaoay and Litao (2021) also investigated teachers' beliefs and practices in implementing performance tasks, which showed that teachers view performance task as valid, meaningful and useful assessment tool which suited to real life application of learning. Teachers had positive attitudes towards collaborative learning but were impeded by workload, timing and other implementation process-related issues. The results indicate that performance tasks are required and necessary but have not been carried out consistently. In addition, Otero and Babaran (2025) assessed the implementation of the Integrated Performance Tasks (IPT) at the institutional level and found that the use of product-based tasks was most frequent, followed by the use of process-based tasks and performance-based tasks. The results show that IPTs were regularly designed and implemented and facilitated authentic learning, collaboration and time management skills. Nonetheless, the study also suggests that continuous training and more established programs are required to help strengthen implementation quality. Moreover, Mutong and Marzan (2024) reported that the performance task mapping revealed opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration and alignment of learning competencies from the curriculum and collaboration perspective. According to their research, performance tasks were often construed as creative presentations, plans and analyses which purported to develop life and career skills. They observed however that misaligned task assignment might lead to an overload for the students. Hence, the need for teacher collaboration. International evidence supports a structural implementation.

According to Heydarnejad et al. (2022), the academic achievement, motivation, and self-efficacy of students improve positively with the use of performance-based assessment as long as it is closely knitted with instruction. Nonetheless, the study emphasized that the effectiveness of performance tasks depends on their systematic design and regular use in the classroom. Studies suggest that although performance task activities are very widely conducted, their effectiveness depends on the clarity of the design of the task, teacher readiness, institutional support and alignment with learning outcomes.

Usefulness of Performance Task Activities in Enhancing Student Learning

Research in the last decade supports that performance task activities can enhance students' cognitive, affective, and skill-based learning outcomes in a significant way. Research studies have shown that performance tasks effectively enhance academic achievement, motivate students, foster comm collaboration, and facilitate the use of learning in real-life settings. As per the study of Ulucinar and Dinç (2021), authentic performance tasks enhance students' self-efficacy, communication, collaboration and motivation. Students thought these tasks were meaningful as it made them see the relation between learning and real life situations. In line with the above, Heydarnejad et al. (2022) indicate learners planned for performance assessment achieved higher levels of academic attainment and self-efficacy over those assessed through conventional means, while also experiencing less anxiety. Performance tasks were found to support

both the academic and psychosocial aspects of learning, thus adding value as assessment tools.

In the Philippines, Omela and Martin (2020) found performance tasks can help students develop better academic skills, attitudes, and instructional engagement. Performance tasks are effective in equipping learners with important learning skills and enhancing their potential. Nonetheless, the research called for continuous monitoring and teacher training to ensure effectiveness. In addition, activity-based and differentiated instructional tasks can enhance participation and retention. Likewise, the student-centered task-based activities were reported to enhance the academic achievement and retention of learners more than teacher-centered activities (Tas & Minaz, 2024). Despite not being entirely focused on performance tasks, the results of their study bolster the value of activity-based, learner-centered strategies that share similar principles with the pedagogy of performance tasks. Numerous studies indicate that performance tasks can be useful but, at the same time, poorly designed or overly excessive tasks may stress and overburden students. Students might be confused and overloaded and might not learn when performance-based tasks are poorly unified or inadequately scaffolded (Mutong & Marzan, 2024; Petalla & Doromal, 2021). The results suggest that performance task activities will have more utility influential when they are purposeful, well-designed, and supported by meaningful criteria and guidance.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of adherence of the respondents to the qualities of effective instructors?
2. What is the level of implementation of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) in terms of instructional practices and learning environment?
3. What is the level of usefulness of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) in terms of academics, attitudes, and instruction?
4. What is the extent of challenges encountered by the respondents in the implementation of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)?
5. Is there a significant difference in the perceived challenges in the implementation of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) when the respondents are grouped according to sex and civil status?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of implementation and the level of usefulness of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study employed a descriptive-normative research design to assess the level of implementation, usefulness, and challenges of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) as perceived by college instructors at the University of La Salette, Inc. This design was appropriate because it allows the systematic description and interpretation of existing conditions, practices, and perceptions without manipulating

variables thereby providing an accurate depiction of the current status of PTE in higher education.

Study Site and Participants. This study was conducted at the University of La Salette, Inc., a private higher education institution located in Santiago City, Isabela. The participants of the study were college instructors currently employed at the university during the time of data collection. A random sampling technique was used to ensure that each instructor had an equal chance of being selected as a respondent.

Population, Sample size, and Sampling Method. A random sampling technique was used to ensure that each instructor had an equal chance of being selected as a respondent. A total of 20 instructors who met the inclusion criteria participated in the study. The inclusion criteria required that the respondents be actively teaching college courses and involved in the implementation of performance-based assessment in their respective subjects. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was secured from all respondents prior to data collection.

Research Instrument. The study utilized a structured questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was designed to gather information relevant to the objectives of the study and was composed of five parts. Part I focused on the respondents' personal circumstances, including selected demographic variables. Part II assessed the qualities of effective instructors, while Part III determined the status of the implementation of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) activities. Part IV measured the level of usefulness of PTE implementation in terms of academics, instruction, and attitudes. Finally, Part V identified the challenges encountered by instructors in the implementation of PTE activities. The instrument was tested for reliability and obtained a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.86, indicating good internal consistency and confirming that the questionnaire was a reliable tool for the study.

Data Analysis. The study used descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequencies, percentages, and ranking was used for the demographic characteristics of the study. Weighted Mean was utilized in treating the data from the adherence, implementation, usefulness, and challenges. The t-test was used to determine the significant difference in the perception of the respondents in the extent of challenges and the implementation of Performance Task Activities when grouped according to sex and civil status. Furthermore, Pearsons r was used to determine the relationship between the usefulness and implementation of Performance Task Activities in the different colleges in the University of La Salette, Inc. The data retrieved through the questionnaire were converted into numerical weights using the 5 Likert scale. The researcher classified and tallied them into different quantities that would enable him to categorize the data.

To compute the extent of adherence of the respondents on the qualities of effective instructors, the following was used:

Points	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Fully Adhered to (FA)
4	3.41-4.20	Adhered to (A)

3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Adhered to (MA)
2	1.81-2.60	Slightly Adhered to (SA)
1	1.00-1.80	Least Adhered to (LA)

To gauge the extent of implementation of the Performance Task Activities, the following scale was used:

Points	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Highly Implemented (FI)
4	3.41-4.20	Implemented (I)
3	2.61-3.40	Slightly Implemented (SI)
2	1.81-2.60	Least Implemented (LI)
1	1.00-1.80	Not Implemented (NI)

To measure the level of usefulness of the performance Task Activities, the following scale was used:

Points	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Very useful (VU)
4	3.41-4.20	Useful (U)
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Useful (MU)
2	1.81-2.60	Less Useful (LU)
1	1.00-1.80	Not Useful (NU)

To gauge the extent of the challenges in the implementation of Performance Task Activities, the following scale was used:

Points	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Very Challenging (VC)
4	3.41-4.20	Challenging (C)
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Challenging (MC)
2	1.81-2.60	Slightly Challenging (SC)
1	1.00-1.80	Least Challenging (LC)

RESULTS

Table 1. <i>Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents</i>		
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	7	35.00
Female	13	65.00
Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	1	5.00
Married	19	95.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelors' Degree	16	80.00

M.A.Ed. Holder	4	20.00
Present Position	Frequency	Percentage
Assistant Instructor I	3	15.00
Assistant Instructor II	0	0.00
Instructor I	17	85.00
Latest Performance Rating	Frequency	Percentage
Very Satisfactory	19	95.00
Satisfactory	1	5.00
No. of Years in service	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	6	30.00
6-10	4	20.00
11-15	3	15.00
16-20	2	10.00
21-25	3	15.00
26-30	2	10.00
Level of In-Service Training	Frequency	Rank
National Level	35	1
Regional Level	17	3
Division Level	28	2
District	0	5
School/University	15	4

A review of the findings (table 1) indicated that the respondents were mostly (65%) female and majority (95%) were married. Eighty percent of the respondents had bachelor's degree and rank of the respondents was 85 percent Instructor I. It shows a well-established group of instructors with strong credibility and experience.

Table 2.
Extent of Adherence of Respondents to the Qualities of Effective Instructors

Particulars	Weighted Mean	QD	Rank
Expert in communication skills	4.35	Fully Adhered to	6
Superior listening skills	4.58	Fully Adhered to	5
Deep knowledge and passion for their subject matter	4.21	Fully Adhered to	10
Has the ability to build caring relationships with students	4.28	Fully Adhered to	9
Has mastery of the subject matter	4.67	Fully Adhered to	2
Excellent preparation and organization skills	4.68	Fully Adhered to	1
Has a strong work ethics	4.31	Fully Adhered to	7
Has a good potential in community-building	4.30	Fully Adhered to	8
Encourage active learning activities	4.59	Fully Adhered to	4

Respect diverse talents and ways of learning	4.61	Fully Adhered to	3
Average Weighted Mean	4.46	Fully Adhered to	

As illustrated in table 2, the overall adherence to the qualities of effective instructors was fully adhered to which has a weighted mean of 4.46. This implies that overall, the instructors are consistent in displaying the essential teaching competencies. Particularly, they are very much prepared and organized (WM = 4.68) and have mastery of subject matter (WM = 4.67).

Table 3.
Status of Performance Task Evaluation Implementation in Terms of Practices

Practices	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) ensures that the learners know exactly what is expected from them, as the unit standard makes it very clear what is required from them.	3.49	Implemented	1
Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) provides well-defined assessment criteria that are clear to both assessors and learners on how the assessment will take place.	3.48	Implemented	2
Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) ensures a more objective assessment and fair result of the predetermined criteria	3.42	Implemented	3
Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) provides a chance for the students to undergo remedial or other corrective actions for learning.	3.47	Implemented	4
Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) requires the students to keep their exams and activities in a portfolio for analysis	3.41	Implemented	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.45	Implemented	

As shown in table 3, the implementation of PTE practices was rated implemented (AWM = 3.45) which indicates that the instructors apply the performance-based assessment in general, mostly in clarifying the expectations of students (WM=3.49) and ensuring fair and objective evaluation (WM=3.42).

Table 4.
Status of Performance Task Evaluation Implementation in Terms of Environment

Environment	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
There is greater support for Performance Evaluation (PTE) from all role-players due to the extensive level of consultation and stakeholder involvement	3.45	Implemented	5
Performance Evaluation (PTE) fosters a better integration between education at school and industry	3.41	Implemented	2
Performance Evaluation (PTE) provides a learning environment that caters to the development of students as future professionals	3.46	Implemented	1
Performance Evaluation (PTE) promotes values formation and character traits ideal for different employment settings	3.44	Implemented	4
Performance Evaluation (PTE) ensures a better way of delivering instruction through appropriate teaching methodology as classroom management	3.42	Implemented	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.43	Implemented	

As a gleaned in table 4, the PTE implementation in terms of environment was also implemented (AWM = 3.43), indicating that the learning environment moderately supports performance-based assessment, particularly in preparing students as future professionals (WM = 3.46).

Table 5.
Level Usefulness of Performance Task Evaluation in terms of Academics

Academics: Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) is useful in...	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Helping the students measure their own performance	3.55	Very Useful	1
Promoting the responsiveness of the school activities towards the enhancement of students' academic performance	3.44	Useful	3
Developing the study habits of the students	3.34	Useful	4
Strengthening the capabilities and skills of the students	3.50	Very Useful	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.46	Useful	

PTE was perceived as useful in academics (AWM = 3.46) as illustrated in table 5, implying that performance tasks help improve students' academic monitoring and skill development, with the strongest effect on self-performance measurement (WM = 3.55).

Table 6. <i>Level Usefulness of Performance Task Evaluation in terms of Attitudes</i>			
Attitudes: Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) is useful in...	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Challenging the students to become more competitive	3.56	Very Useful	1
Practicing collaboration rather than competition	3.48	Useful	4
Creating a mindset towards a clear direction of learning	3.41	Useful	5
Motivating the students to be independent	3.50	Very Useful	3
Helping learners to accept responsibility for learning, as they are now at the center of the learning process	3.53	Very Useful	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.50	Very Useful	

Based on table 6, the attitudes on PTE was rated very useful (AWM = 3.50), meaning that performance tasks positively influence student motivation, responsibility, and competitiveness, especially in encouraging accountability for learning (WM = 3.53).

Table 7. <i>Level Usefulness of Performance Task Evaluation in terms of Instruction</i>			
Instruction: Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) is useful in...	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Requiring faculty members to master their subjects being handled	3.38	Useful	2
Simplifying the execution of the lessons	3.37	Useful	3.5
Asking the instructors to be more of a facilitator than a lecturer	3.48	Useful	1
Creating a conducive atmosphere for the teaching and learning process	3.27	Useful	5
Providing the learning skills necessary for the industry	3.37	Useful	3.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.37	Useful	

The result presented in table 7 PTE usefulness in instruction was rated useful (AWM = 3.37), indicating that performance tasks support effective teaching practices by encouraging instructors to act more as facilitators rather than traditional lecturers (WM = 3.48)

Extent of Challenges in the Implementation Performance Task Evaluation

Table 8. <i>Extent of challenges in the implementation of Performance Task Evaluation as perceived by the Instructors</i>			
Particulars	Weighted Mean	QD	Rank
Non-Utilization of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)- technology-based in teaching social	2.75	Moderately Challenging	14
Inability of instructors to inspire and instill the skills of questioning, thinking, judging, discussion and analysis in the students	2.71	Moderately Challenging	15
Failure of Instructors to expose all students to be exposed to field study and inquiry projects	2.80	Moderately Challenging	11.5
Instructors are not adequately informed of the objectives of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)	3.40	Moderately Challenging	4
Instructors preferred to use the traditional type of techniques rather than Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)	3.24	Moderately Challenging	7
Some strategies used in Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) by the Instructors are not suited to the nature of the subject matter and learners	3.28	Moderately Challenging	6
Failure to stimulate the student's interest in the subject and activities by using a variety of suitable motivational devices through Performance Task Evaluation (PTE).	2.79	Moderately Challenging	13
Through Performance Task Evaluation (PTE), instructors has an inability to arouse the interest of the class by relating subject matter to their important needs or goals.	2.80	Moderately Challenging	11.5
Lack of knowledge in the proper classification of behavioral objectives and goals in Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)	2.92	Moderately Challenging	10
Lack of available resources (time, Information, materials, etc).	3.28	Moderately Challenging	5
The incompatibility of interest of the instructors	3.21	Moderately Challenging	8
Lack of motivation by the deans to introduce Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)	3.20	Moderately Challenging	9
There is a poor technical support from those meant to implement Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)	4.25	Very Challenging	3

Negative attitude towards supervision and evaluation	4.55	Very Challenging	1
Failure of Instructors to evaluate students' performance daily	4.51	Very Challenging	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.31	Moderately Challenging	

Presented in table 8 the overall level of challenges in implementing PTE was moderately challenging (AWM = 3.31), implying that while implementation is feasible, instructors face notable difficulties, particularly negative attitudes toward supervision (WM = 4.55) and lack of daily performance evaluation (WM = 4.51).

Test of Difference on the perception on the problem encountered in the implementation of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) when grouped according to sex and civil status.

Table 9.
Independent T-test computation on the perception of problems encountered in Performance Task Evaluation by the Instructors when grouped according to Sex

	Sex	Mean	Description	t-value	p-value	Decision
Challenges in the implementation of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)	Male	3.90	Very Challenging	-2.474	0.018	Reject Ho
	Female	4.26	Very Challenging			

Table 9 demonstrate that there is a significant difference in perceived challenges that was found when grouped by sex ($p = 0.018$), indicating that female instructors ($M = 4.26$) experience greater challenges in PTE implementation compared to male instructors ($M = 3.90$).

Table 10.
Independent T-test computation on the perception of problems encountered in Performance Task Evaluation by the Instructors when grouped according to Civil Status

	Sex	Mean	Description	t-value	p-value	Decision
Challenges in the implementation of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE)	Single	4.04	Very Challenging	7.298	0.002	Reject Ho
	Married	4.17	Very Challenging			

Reflected in table 10, there was also a significant difference in perceived challenges when grouped by civil status ($p = 0.002$), suggesting that married instructors ($M = 4.17$) perceive slightly higher implementation challenges than single instructors ($M = 4.04$).

Test of Relationship between the extent of implementation and the level of usefulness of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) in Higher Education Institution

Table 11. <i>Pearson-r correlation coefficient between the extent of implementation and the level of usefulness of Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) as perceived by the instructors in Higher Education Institution</i>		
	r-value	Interpretation
Status of implementation vs. Level of Usefulness	0.688777	Significant

As table 11 illustrates that the significant positive correlation between the extent of PTE implementation and level of usefulness ($r = 0.689$) indicates that better and more consistent implementation of performance tasks leads to higher perceived benefits in teaching and learning.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study indicate that Performance Task Evaluation (PTE) was implemented and perceived as useful to very useful across academic, instructional, and attitudinal domains, while challenges encountered by instructors were generally moderate. The results show that PTE is a viable and useful assessment approach, which should be well supported to allow for consistency and effectiveness.

The favorable perception of PTE as an aid to improve academic results and learner attitudes finds support in the study by Yaghoubi et al. (2025), who report that performance-based assessment significantly improved students' academic motivation, resilience and perceived teacher support. Also, the current study indicated that PTE was useful in the measuring process of students' own performance and making them responsible for learning. Hence, structured performance task aligns with learner-centered outcomes. Despite Yaghoubi et al.'s focus on technology-oriented contexts, the present findings suggest that benefits can be achieved despite a moderate-level implementation constraint.

According to Heydarnejad et al. (2022), performance assessment positively influences learners' academic achievement and motivation compared to traditional assessment, corroborating the present findings. In Student's Account PTE was very useful in changing student attitude to a positive, for instance, independent, competitive, and responsible. In contrast to situations where assessment reform encounters fierce opposition, the current study's instructors appear to accept PTE, as indicated by their implementation and usefulness ratings in this study. The moderate challenge level reported by the instructors is consistent with Kearney et al. (2021) who found that teachers generally favor performance-based and classroom-based assessments and face manageable challenges related to workload, time and assessment design. The challenges noted in this study would not impede implementation, rather they illuminate

effective practice and offer insight into ways professional learning and organizational support could enhance the practice. In addition, the positive relationship between the extent of PTE implementation and the perceived usefulness of the PTE confirms the argument of Panadero et al. (2022), who argued that quality implementation of formative and performance-based assessment enhances teaching and learning. This means that if the instructors become more consistent and comfortable using PTE, then the educational benefits of PTE would be further enhanced. Lastly, the differences in perceived challenges when grouped by sex and civil status suggest that the professional experience of the instructors affects the perception of assessment demands. Demographic and contextual influences shape educators' engagement with assessment reforms in the view of DeLuca et al. (2021) Despite this variance, overall challenges perceptions fell within a moderate range, otherwise affirming that PTE implementation is feasible and sustainable in the institution.

Conclusions

Results show that performance tasks are regularly given in the University of La Salette, Inc. and it is considered useful or very useful in improving academic performance, student attitudes and instructional practices. The results show that the teachers demonstrate a strong commitment to the attributes of a good teacher. In addition to this, there is a positive relationship between level of implementation and perceived usefulness of PTE. More effective implementation results in more educational benefits. Implementation challenges do exist, especially in terms of supervision, workload and technical support. The challenges are mainly moderate and manageable. Therefore, PTE is a sustainable and viable assessment method for HEIs.

Recommendations

The findings suggests that Philippine higher education institutions can enhance learner-centered and outcomes-based education by institutionalizing properly designed performance task assessment. Proper implementation of PTE enhances the focus of the school on the necessary skills of the new millennium. As a result, the students take charge of their learning. Simultaneously, the faculty members play a facilitative and authentic role during the teaching-learning process. However, institutions should also remember that the assessment reform will not be consistent and equitable across colleges and faculty profiles without systemic support, that is professional development, clear guidelines and positive supervisory practices. In addition, it is advisable for higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines to have a clear institutional policies and frameworks for the implementation of performance tasks and maintain its standards; continuous training on assessment design and feedback for faculty/instructors; and the enhancement of technical administrative support systems. Finally, it is also suggested a need to strengthen collaborative faculty planning, along with supportive instructional leadership, to help ease implementation and workload challenges. By taking this measure, the institutions will enhance the educational quality of performance tasks to improve learning growth. These will help in quality higher education standards at the national and global levels.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers made vigorous effort to protect the anonymity of all respondents and made sure that the consent to participate in data collection was free and voluntary. Data collected was strictly kept confidential, well archived and disposed of at the end of the study. Secrecy was maintained at all levels of the research process. The researchers also made every effort to prevent plagiarism, which ensured that the analysis and interpretation of findings were not biased at all. The research was conducted in full compliance with the standards of academic integrity, and all results were kept confidential, intended solely to serve academic purposes

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